

Molar Volume of Calcium Acetate in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of calcium acetate has been determined in 10, 20, 30 and 40% aqueous acetic acid at different temperatures. Results have been interpreted in terms of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions and structure making/structure breaking capacity. The apparent molar expansibility (ϕ°_E) has also been determined. Calcium acetate has been found to be structure breaker.

The study of apparent molar volumes of electrolytes at infinite dilution and their dependence on temperature can furnish useful information on the nature of solute-solvent interactions¹. Blokhra and Verma studied acetates of lithium and sodium in aqueous methyl acetate^{2,3} and ammonium salts in aqueous acetic acid from the view-point of solute-solvent interactions. In all the cases the stress was laid on 1 : 1 electrolytes in binary solvent. In the present communication studies with calcium acetate in aqueous acetic acid are described. Calcium acetate in aqueous acetic acid was selected because it has common ion with the solvent and solute having common ion with the solvent may produce interesting results from both theoretical and experimental view-points of solution chemistry. In order to know about the nature of the solute-solvent interaction, molar volume of calcium acetate in aqueous acetic acid was determined and discussed in the present communication.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume has been calculated from density data by using equation (1)⁴

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d_0} - \frac{1000(d-d_0)}{Cd_0} \quad (1)$$

where d_0 is the density of solvent, d the density of solution, C the molarity of solution and M_2 the molecular weight of salt. Errors in ϕ_v were calculated from equation (2)⁵,

$$\Delta\phi_v = (2\Delta d/d^2)(1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) assumes errors to be associated with the density of solution (d) and solvent (d_0). Moreover, errors associated with determination of solution concentration are not the limiting factor while calculating the apparent molar volumes. The errors as derived from equation (2) was estimated to range from $\pm 0.01 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.01 M concentration to $\pm 0.13 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.12 M concentration.

Limiting apparent molar volume has been

calculated with the help of Redlich and Meyer's equation^{5,6},

$$\frac{\phi_v - \phi_v^{\circ}}{\sqrt{m}} = S_v + b_v \sqrt{m}$$

The plots of $(\phi_v - \phi_v^{\circ})/\sqrt{m}$ vs \sqrt{m} were adjusted for different values of ϕ_v° in order to have best-fit. Approximate value for ϕ_v° , however, was taken from plot of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{m} . The values of limiting molar volume, slope and intercept are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF ϕ_v° , S_v AND b_v FOR CALCIUM ACETATE IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Acetic acid %	Temp. K	ϕ_v° $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	S_v $\text{cm}^3 \text{ L}^{1/2} \text{ mol}^{-3/2}$	b_v $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-2}$
10	303.0	61.20	+ 44.44	+ 37.0
20	303.0	49.70	+ 25.56	+ 53.6
30	303.0	63.00	+ 29.78	+ 44.2
40	303.0	32.00	+100.00	+119.6
10	298.0	26.00	+ 41.03	+125.6
10	308.0	72.00	+ 68.97	- 73.6
10	313.0	57.00	+ 97.78	+106.2

The intercept S_v in Redlich equation may be attributed to a measure of ion-ion or solute-solute interaction. It is obvious from the magnitude of S_v that ion-ion interaction is strongest in 40% acetic acid and weakest in 20% acetic acid at 303 K. Ion-ion interaction increases with increase in temperature. The empirical constant b_v seems to be the function of concentration of solvent and temperature. It increases with increasing content of acetic acid, however, it decreases with temperature and has a maximum decrease at 308 K.

ϕ_v° is a measure of solute-solvent interaction. Its magnitude is positive in all the cases thereby suggesting strong solute-solvent interactions. ϕ_v° first increases with increasing amount of acetic acid and attains a maximum. Solute-solvent interaction

is maximum in 30% acetic acid and minimum in 40% acetic acid at 303 K. In 30% acetic acid, there is maximum solvation and hence maximum solute-solvent interaction. In 40% acetic acid, ϕ_v^0 decreases which means that solute-solvent interaction decreases due to the establishment of ionic equilibrium in the solvent system. Solute-solvent interaction increases with increase in temperature upto 308 K and at 313 K there is a decrease in the solute-solvent interaction. The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 in 10% acetic acid can be expressed by equation (4),

$$\phi_v^0 = -39877.9 + 260.424t - 0.4240t^2 \quad (4)$$

where, t is the temperature in degree Celsius.

The apparent molar expansibility, $\phi_E^0 = (\delta^2 \phi_v^0 / \delta t^2)$ calculated from equation (4) has been found to decrease with temperature (Table 2). The decrease in expansibility with temperature shows that calcium acetate behaves like a common electrolyte in 10% aqueous acetic acid.

The structure-making/breaking capacity of calcium acetate was deduced with the help of Hepler's reasoning⁶, i.e. on the basis of the sign of $(\delta^2 \phi_v^0 / \delta t^2)$. It has been deduced from general thermodynamic equation (5),

$$(\delta \bar{C}_p / \delta p)_T = -(\delta^2 \phi_v^0 / \delta t^2)_p \quad (5)$$

From equation (5) it is clear that a structure-making solute should have a positive value of $(\delta^2 \phi_v^0 / \delta t^2)_p$; in case of calcium acetate, this value has been found to be negative. This shows that calcium acetate is a structure-breaker. Similar conclusion is drawn from Walden product⁷.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ϕ_E^0 OF CALCIUM ACETATE IN 10% AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	ϕ_E^0 cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
298.0	9.44
303.0	4.48
308.0	-0.48
313.0	-5.44

Experimental

Water used for solution had specific conductance in the range $0.1-1.0 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Calcium acetate (G.R.) was dried in vacuum desiccator. Acetic acid was of G.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared by weight and conversion of molality to molarity was made by the expression described elsewhere⁸. Density was determined with the help of apparatus as described by Ward and Millero⁹.

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